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**METHODS OF ASSESSING THE POSSIBILITY OF EXCLUSIONS IN
INFORMATION PROTECTION**

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Abstract. This article analyzes the structure and principles of constructing an automated information security system; based on mathematical methods, possible situations of bypassing it are substantiated; as a result, a two-way closed virtual information security shell is created. Based on a mathematical approach, the system delay time was considered as a random variable.

Keywords: information, security, system, probability, virtual, failure, random, protection, development, model.

INTRODUCTION

It is no secret that the problem of security in the world today is one of the main tasks requiring increased attention. Information security is of great importance, and the demand for it is growing every day. Every hour new viruses and malware are developed, new algorithms and various methods of bypassing existing encryption methods are created, so timely response to new attacks and not only identifying the threat, but also managing it is the call of the hour [1-3].

Research methodology. Based on the results of the study, one of the main parameters is to determine the types of possible channels of unauthorized access to protected information and their quantity,

according to the model of the intruder in the system. It is these channels that are technically divided into managed and unmanaged. For example, logging into a system using a terminal keyboard may be controlled by a special program, but the communication channels of a regionally distributed system are not always controlled. Based on channel analysis, you must be prepared to block these channels or use new security measures [1].

Assets are identified at the second stage of identification and assessment of resources - "Identification and assessment of assets" [3, 5]. Calculating the value of information assets allows you to determine the adequacy of the proposed controls and protection.

At the third stage of assessing threats and vulnerabilities - "Risk and Vulnerability Assessment" - threats and vulnerabilities of the organization's information assets are identified and assessed [3,6]. The commercial version of the CRAMM method uses the following set of criteria for such assessment and identification (consequences of information security threats):

- 1 - criterion - harm to the organization's reputation
- 2 - financial losses associated with resource recovery;
- 3 - disorder in the company;
- 4 - financial losses from disclosure and transfer of information to competitors, as well as other criteria.

Results and analysis. Based on the results obtained, determining the list of threats and creating an attacker model is considered a mandatory stage in the design of a security system. The list of possible security threats for each system, as well as the characteristics of a possible attacker, are individual. Therefore, the list and model should be unofficial. Information security is ensured only if the perceived threats and qualities of the attacker correspond to the real situation. If there is a vulnerability in the system, a potential security threat can be implemented in the form of an attack.

As a result of interference, each element sent may be recognized by the recipient as $y_k (y_k \neq x_i)$. Since this process is error-prone, the constant message $x(t)$ can be taken to be $y(t) \neq ax(t - \tau)$ for all or some times, where a and τ are constants that are usually not informationally significant. From the point of view of information theory, the physical structure of the communication channel is not important. In this case, the channel properties are described by the complete transition probability matrix $P(x_i/y_k)$ or $P(y_k/x_i)$, if the received element is finite, then the probability of sending element y_k is finite $P(x_i/y_k)$ and $P(y_k/x_i)$ probability obtaining element x_i is equal to y_k . It is assumed that new elements cannot be created due to interference.

If we $\Delta u \ll U_{max} - U_{min}$ for a sufficiently small excess Δu $P_U(u)$ is a constant and current value $P_i = P_U(u_i)\Delta u$. The mathematical expectation of noise at the i -step interval is written as follows[4]:

$$M[\xi_i] = P_i \int_{u_{i-1/2}}^{u_{i+1/2}} (u - u_i) du = \frac{1}{2} P_i [(u_{i+1/2} - u_i)^2 - (u_{i-1/2} - u_i)^2].$$

The noise variance in the i -step interval is expressed as follows:

$$D[\xi_i] = P_i \int_{u_{i-\frac{1}{2}}}^{u_{i+\frac{1}{2}}} (u - u_i)^2 du = \frac{1}{3} P_i [(u_{i+\frac{1}{2}} - u_i)^3 - (u_{i-\frac{1}{2}} - u_i)^3].$$

Equating the first derivative to zero, we find the minimum variance

$$D[\xi] = \frac{\Delta u^2}{12}.$$

Now we can evaluate the reliability of the quantized message by the message ratio $\frac{P_c}{P_w}$, medium power P_w , quantization noise power. P_c - The quantization noise power is calculated using the following formula:

$$P_w = \sigma_\xi^2 = \frac{1}{\Delta u} \int_{-\frac{\Delta u}{2}}^{+\frac{\Delta u}{2}} \xi^2 d\xi = \frac{\Delta u^2}{12} ;;$$

The average message power is calculated using the formula

$$P_c = \sigma_u^2 = \frac{1}{2U_M} \int_{-U_M}^{+U_M} u^2 dy = \frac{U_M^2}{3}.$$

Quantization accuracy is easy to evaluate $P_k = (2 \frac{U_M}{\Delta u})^2$.

Conclusion. One of the main problems of the current information age is the improvement of methods and means of protection against accidental and intentional threats. Quantitative assessment of its vulnerability is of great importance when solving practical problems of information security. To protect against random threats, it is recommended to use methods and means to increase the reliability of automated systems.

Based on the results of the study, one of the main parameters is to determine the types and number of possible channels for unauthorized access to protected information in accordance with the model of the intruder in the system, and it is planned that these channels will be controlled by a special program for logging into the system through the keyboard of the technical control terminal. But communication channels of a regionally distributed system are not always manageable. Based on the analysis of channels, the readiness to block these channels is determined, analyzing its structure and principles of construction, possible cases of bypassing it are determined and measures to eliminate it are planned, as a result of which a closed virtual information security shell is created. created.

The mathematical model for designing a two-way closed virtual shell took into account the presence of a signal part and a risk (malfunction) in the data of the observed object when processing information in the form of a signal. In this case, the signal, as a component of the measured field, carrying information about the object of interest to us, is often carried out in unavoidable noise conditions, therefore, to overcome these obstacles, the reliability of the quantized message was assessed using the method of the

ratio of the average message power to the power of the quantization noise, as a consequence of the quantization noise. A mathematical model of power has been developed.

As a general conclusion, it can be noted that in order to prevent successful attacks, it is necessary to look for and analyze the weaknesses of the system. It is necessary to analyze vulnerabilities depending on the source of the vulnerability, the level of risk, the level of distribution, which requires compliance with the mandatory procedure for certification of an information object and their periodic analysis at a pre-certified object.

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